

Location of the regions (loci) with significant correlation between genotype of RFLP markers and blast field resistance in Japanese upland rice.

markers and resistance/susceptibility in the F_3 lines. We found a close relationship between blast resistance and genotypic frequency in eight regions of six chromosomes. One region was detected each on chromosomes 2, 6, 7, and 12; two regions were detected on chromosomes 4 and 11 (see figure). The loci linked to RFLP markers on chromosomes 4 and 11 played a major role in expressing field resistance, confirming the results of an earlier study (Wang et al 1994).

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Genetic analysis for true resistance to blast in rice varieties

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Analysis of unknown blast resistance gene(s) of introduced or improved indica varieties showing high blast resistance is useful. We estimated the true resistance genes of indica varieties IR50, Suweon 288 (IR24//IR24/IR747), and Takanari (Milyang 42/Milyang 25) using the method of Toriyama et al (1983), in which backcrossed progenies are tested for reactions to blast isolates of different races.

IR50 was crossed with Ouu308, a japonica line having only the *Pi-a* gene. Resulting F_1 plants were backcrossed with parent Ouu308 to obtain B_1F_2 lines. We inoculated 141 lines of the B_1F_2 with blast isolate TH68-141 (race 003, compatible to *Pi-a* only) to estimate the number of true resistance genes involved. The ratio of the B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total B_1F_2 lines tested was 17.0%, indicating that IR50 has two or three true resistance genes, exclusive of *Pi-a* (Table 1). All 24 B_1F_2

Table 1. Expected and actual ratios of B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total B_1F_2 lines tested for different numbers of true resistance genes involved (except for *Pi-a*).

Genes involved (no.)	2	3	4	5	6
Expected ratio	25.0	12.5	6.3	3.1	1.6
Actual ratio					
IR50	17.0				
Suweon 288				3.0	
Takanari		13.0			

Table 2. Blast isolates of different races used and the corresponding true resistance genes.

Isolate (race)	TH 68-141 (003)	Naga 69-150 (007)	NAO -02 (033)	Ina N86-95A (047)	TH 67-106 (103)	Ina 85-101 (303)	5A (403)	TH 87-20 (007-b ⁺)
Compatible gene(s) for true resistance	<i>Pi-a</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-k</i> <i>Pi-k^m</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i> <i>Pi-z</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-ta</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-ta</i> <i>Pi-ta²</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-z^t</i>	<i>Pi-a</i> <i>Pi-i</i> <i>Pi-b</i>

lines fixed for susceptibility to TH68-141 showed resistance to blast isolate Naga66-16 (race 001, incompatible to *Pi-a* gene), indicating that IR50 has the *Pi-a* gene. We selected 29 of the B_1F_2 lines showing the segregation ratio of 3 resistant: 1 susceptible plants against TH68-141 and inoculated these with seven isolates of different races (Table 2). Of these, eight lines showed susceptibility to isolate TH87-20 (race 007-b⁺, compatible to *Pi-a*, *Pi-i*, and *Pi-b*) despite showing segregation against isolate Naga69-50 (race 007, compatible to *Pi-a* and *Pi-i*). This indicates that IR50 also has the *Pi-b* gene. Based on the response of the lines to other isolates, it was difficult to estimate other true resistance genes in IR50 (Table 2). The results suggest that IR50 has the *Pi-a*, *Pi-b*, and one or two true resistance genes.

Suweon 288 and Takanari were backcrossed with variety Nekken 2, which has the *Pi-a* and *S-5ⁿ* (wide-compatibility gene to reduce hybrid sterility). We inoculated 100 lines of these B_1F_2 with blast isolate TH68-141. The ratio of B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to the total lines tested were 3.0 and 13.0%, respectively, indicating that Suweon 288 has four to six genes and Takanari has three genes, exclusive of *Pi-a* (Table 1). Both varieties were verified to have the *Pi-a* gene after inoculation with isolate Naga66-16, with 3 and 13 of the B_1F_2 lines fixed for susceptibility to TH68-141, respectively. When seven isolates (Table 2) were used to check 28 and 50 of the B_1F_2 lines showing the segregation against TH68-141 respectively for the two varieties, only Takanari was proven to have the *Pi-b* gene based on the line's response to isolates Naga69-150 and TH87-20. The results suggest that Suweon 288 has *Pi-a* and four to six other genes. Takanari, on the other hand, has *Pi-a*, *Pi-b*, and two other genes.

Some of the genes we failed to identify in this study are probably new resistance genes, including recessive ones.

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Note to readers

To save on costs, the IRRN is now being published three times a year: April, August, and December. We have also discontinued the IRRN sections on news about research collaboration and announcements. The material previously covered in these sections is now included in the *Rice Reporter*.

Pest resistance—insects

Preliminary evidence of aphid resistance in transgenic plants

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Sap-sucking insect pests (mainly Homoptera) can severely damage rice crops and also transmit virus diseases. Promising results have already been achieved with transgenic plants expressing the *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) delta-endotoxin gene and proteinase inhibitor genes, which protect plants from Lepidoptera and Coleoptera insect pests, but are not effective against Homoptera insects. Information from this study, which describes pea lectin (*P-lec*) transgenic tobacco plants showing apparent aphid resistance, may be valuable for controlling rice Homoptera insect pests.

Plant expression plasmid constructed. We cloned and identified the *P-lec* gene as described by Liu et al (1995). A *HindIII/SacI* fragment from *pBS-lec1*, including 0.9-kb *P-lec* gene, was inserted into mini Ti-plasmid pK7-1, regulated by CaMV35S promoter in the 5'-end and *rbcS* Poly(A) signal in the 3'-end. The recombinant was

then transferred into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* LBA4404 by electroporation.

Plant transformation. Leaf discs of tobacco line NC89 were transformed via *A. tumefaciens*. Transformants were selected using kanamycin, and the transgenic plants were confirmed using Npt-II assay.

Bioassay on transgenic plants. Young transgenic tobacco plants and control tobacco plants (4-5 leaves) were individually infested on the top leaves with 80 peach aphids (*Myzus persicae*). Aphid population density was calculated 4 and 6 wk after infestation and used to assign the resistance score (see table).

We evaluated aphid resistance (divided into four resistance levels) based on density of aphid population on the top leaves. The ratio of plants with high resistance to aphids (scores 3 and 4) and the resistance mean in transgenic plants were higher than in the control (see table), indicating that the transgenic plants had better protection from aphids than the control (see figure).

A dramatic difference exists in aphid resistance between the transgenic tobacco and the control, possibly caused by transgenic plants expressing *P-lec*. However, evidence indicating the effect of pea lectin against some sap-sucking insect pests fed

Leaves from transgenic tobacco plant (right) and from control tobacco plant. The photo was taken 6 wk after aphid infestation.

on an artificial diet is not available (Powell et al 1993). Possible explanations for this area) the effects of pea lectin on rice brown planthopper and rice green leafhopper used in Powell's study differed from the effects on aphids, and b) the pea lectin could have lost its antimetabolic activity on Homoptera insects during the artificial diet preparation.

The *P-lec* gene expression plasmid suitable for rice transformation has already been constructed, and the transformation of rice is under way.

Bioassay of transgenic and control tobacco plants.

Score ^a	Weeks after infestation ^b							
	4				6			
	Plants (no.)	Control (%)	Plants (no.)	<i>P-lec</i> (%)	Plants (no.)	Control (%)	Plants (no.)	<i>P-lec</i> (%)
1	21	61.8	8	27.6	27	79.4	8	27.6
2	5	14.9	4	13.8	5	14.7	8	27.6
3	2	5.9	7	24.1	2	5.9	4	13.8
4	6	17.6	10	54.5	0	0.0	9	31.0
Total	34		29		34		29	

^a4 = plants where peach aphid population density on top leaves is less than 2 aphids cm² leaf; 3 = density is between 2 and 5 aphids cm⁻¹ leaf; 2 = density is in the range of 1-50; and 1 = density of more than 10 aphids cm⁻² leaf. ^bData represent percentage of particular plants to total plants infested.

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